

Orisa Popo Religious Group

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Orisa popo is the foundational and a highly revered deity of Ogbomoso Kingdom, Oyo State, Nigeria. It is regarded as the patron deity of the land. It has been closely associated with the land since its founding. Documentary evidence supports the influence of the deity among the people especially in the last four centuries (more specifically since the 17th century). Ogbomoso, a prominent city in Oyo State, Nigeria, was founded in the mid 17th century by prominent personalities who were all professional hunters although groups of people had been living around the area for centuries, the city of Ogbomoso was not organised under a central ruler until this time. The most renown of the hunters/warriors who founded the city was Soun Olabanjo Ogunlola, a fearless hunter who became the first baale of the land. History has it that Soun Ogunlola and his wife, Eesu migrated to the then dense forest around 1650 and settled under a tree called ijagbon tree. This initial settlement became the elegant palace today and, the then initial settlement of the couple (a hut) gradually metamorphosed into the modern city of Ogbomoso. It is perhaps pertinent to mention that the worship of orisa popo was initiated by Eesu, the wife of the soun who located its shrine in a conspicuous place along the north- south trade routes. This conspicuous location gave the deity its name Orisa popo; orisa, meaning 'deity' and popo meaning 'high way' in Yoruba diction. The deity was closely associated with the founding of the city and people from far and near (including passers-by) participated in its worship. For this reason, the deity is closely tied to the indigenous palace and native authority of Ogbomoso kingdom. It is also for this reason that, all indigenes of Ogbomoso are considered adherents of the religious tradition, irrespective of other religious groups such (Islam and Christianity) they are identified with. As a matter of fact, the religious life of Ogbomoso people is notably syncretic in the sense that many of those who profess Christianity and Islamic faiths also participate in the worship of the deities in one way or another. Some are actively involved in popo festival and rituals while some visit the shrine and its priests for spiritual consultations (divination), protective power, solution to problem of infertility for barren women and financial prosperity wealth (aje). The earliest devotees or worshipers were the traditional rulers, the priests, members of the royal houses, warriors of the land, the palace guards. They all believed that the deity provides guidance and protection for the kingdom. The deity is worshiped with the following items: palm oil, cola-nut, bitter cola, emu (palm wine), efun (white local chalk), osun (a traditional red powder commonly mixed with shea butter-ori), ewe isegun, adie (fowl), ewure (goat), isu (yam), ewa (beans), and omi mimo (very clean water). The taboos associated with the deity are that: no one should make mockery of the deity either (publicly or secretly) as this may arouse its anger and cause devastating effects; no one, except the priests and priestesses should access certain sacred or forbidden spots in the shrine. Drinking palm wine at the shrine and stealing items dedicated to the deity are major offenses. It is believed that violation of these taboos may lead to unexplained sicknesses or accident. Prayers offered to the deity is believed to be potent to ward-off or heal sickness, prevent untimely death, give children to barren women, protect individuals and the city from

dangers (such as invasion by external force) and; bring about peace and prosperity to the community.. The city derives its name from a combination of terms showcasing the valour of the first ruler. Ogunlola had fought gallantly against and defeated a group of bandits headed by a notorious one called Elemoso who for years terrorised the entire region of the old Oyo empire (Ogbomoso was then a settlement within the great Oyo Empire). Ogunlola fought and killed Elemoso and took the severed head of the latter to the paramount ruler, the Alaafin of Oyo who was so impressed that he rewarded him with the chiefdom of the settlement and asked him to take custody of Elemoso's head. He told him to go and begin to administer the territory of Ogbomoso in Yoruba language. The word "ma lo s'oun or lo maa s'oun" were the expressions of the Alaafin to Ogunlola. So the official title of the ruler of the community became "Soun". From that time on, his settlement became known as the place of "the one who severed and carried the head of Elemoso" (ogbori elemoso) which later became shortened as Ogbomoso. The following are some of the cultural significance of the deity:

1. Cosmic Importance: Orisa popo is believed to be an avatar of Orisa nla or Obatala, the Yoruba arch divinity associated with the creation of the universe. In this myth, It is strongly believed that Obatala's role in the creation was the molding of human bodies, specially the head while the highest supreme being, Olodumare gave life to the body. Thus, orisa popo gave a kind of cosmological myth to its adherents.
2. Spiritual Fortification: The now city of Ogbomoso at the foundational stage was prone several attacks by various powers and groups of Bandits. Indigenes relied heavily on the support of the deity for their protection. Such is the protective power of the deity in the people belief. It also served as spiritual anchor and protection for refugees who flocked to Ogbomoso during the 19th century wars and Fulani invasions
3. Guidance: In ancient times also the priests and priestesses of the deity were very prominent and influential as people relied on their spiritual guidance and prosperity of the city.

Date Range: 1601 CE - 2025 CE

Region: Ogbomoso

Region tags: Western Africa, Nigeria, Oyo State, Africa

Ogbomoso Kingdom from 1601

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Neimark, Philip . The Way of the Orisa: Empowering Your Life Through the Ancient African Religions of Ifa. San Francisco: Harper, 1993.
- Source 2: Akanji, Isaac . Orisa Popo Divinity: A Theological Esperience in Ogbomosoland. A Thesis Presented to the Faculty of the NBTS. Ogbomoso: Nigeria Baptist Theological Seminary, 1999.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: Kamil, Hamza, and Malang Fanneh. "Challenges of Urbanization in Post-Colonial Ogbomoso, 1990-2019." *Akwa Journal of History (AJOH)* 1, no. 1 (2023): 104–28.

– Source 1 Description: Lawuyi, O. B. "The Obatala Factor in Yoruba History." *History in Africa* 19 (1992): 369–75.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: Check out this video, "orisa popo ogbomoso beliefs"
<https://share.google/5XckO2ssmKCVafhrk>

Notes: Lyrics/song of orisa popo Yoruba Orisa popo temi ni o ba mi se o bi mo se ndun yunmuyunmu si o leti, temi o bami se. Bi won ba nsoro fun o lehin mama gbao, temi ni o ba mi se. English Translation Orisa popo, attend to my own request, as I impress my concerns to your hearing always, attend to my request. If enemies are trying to back bite me, do not listen to them, just attend to my prayers.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Notes: The religion is in cultural contact with other religious groups of Christianity, Islam and other brand of Yoruba Indigenous Religion. However, the contact is not of competitive nature.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The cultural contact is highly accommodating and pluralistic in nature. Orisa Popo is the foundational patron divinity of the Ogbomoso kingdom, therefore, every indigene of the kingdom is accommodated irrespective of their other religious affiliation.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: The cultural contact is neutral of any form of bias or sentiment. Since the religion

embraces every indigene of the community, it does not seek to convert them.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: Orisa Popo being considered as the foundational Patron divinity of Ogbomoso kingdom is not in contestation with any other religious groups. Rather, its considered the mother of all other religious groups in the kingdom.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: Orisa Popo is not in contestation with any other religious groups. Its primary place of operation is within the kingdom, as a result, has no such interaction with groups outside of the community.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: The religion does not assign group affiliation. since the religion is believed to be mother of all in the kingdom, other groups belong to it and does not have such system of assigning groups to its children.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not proselytize or recruits new members since all indigenes are considered to be its members irrespective of whether they have other religious affiliations or not.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

Notes: Orisa Popo is closely attached to the indigenous administration of Ogbomoso kingdom and as a result, the priest receives subventions from the palace rather than monthly salary.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not construct infrastructure other than the temple located within the palace. Therefore, the indigenous administration does not pay for religious infrastructure.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Yes

Notes: The King is considered the highest-ranking leader of the religious group. However, there are priests directly associated to the deity who carry out sacrificial and spiritual duties on behalf of the king.

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Yes

Notes: In the local community, the political leaders are inseparable from the religious leaders. Most of the priests are chiefs in the palace. So, the priests combine roles both as spiritual leaders and community administrative leaders.

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

Notes: The observance of Orisa Popo is largely voluntary although encouraged. The community believes that some people's absence at the function does not disqualify them from being practitioners.

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Yes

Notes: Although the local community is inclined to the governance of their affairs by customary codes, however, the legal code of the country takes pre-eminence over customary codes as they will not stand when challenged in the law court if they differ from the latter.

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Notes: The devotees who receive subventions from the King are exempted from paying tax. However, the practitioners who constitute the populace of the kingdom are not exempted

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: The religion does not entertain the conception of apostasy. The group considered any indigene of the kingdom a practitioner including those affiliated to other religious groups.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 710000

Notes: The population of the kingdom is estimated to be about 600,000 according to the last census in 2006 and now projected to be about 710,000. Although not all the indigenes currently openly associate themselves with the religious group.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 10

Notes: The general belief is that all indigenes are practitioners as captured in the local (Yoruba) expression: Gbogbo wa ni omo Orisa Popo (We all are children of Orisa Popo). However, in practice, not all indigenes and residents of the city subscribe to the group membership.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Notes: Orisa Popo is the mother of all religions in the sample region embracing all indigenes as its adherents. Although, some people who identify with Orisa Popo religious group may also lay claim to other religious groups. In addition, not every indigene or resident of the city professes membership of the religious group.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– No

Notes: The King is considered the highest-ranking leader of Orisa Popo. There are also community leaders among the priests who doubles are both priest and chief in the community.

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

Notes: There is a clear hierarchy with Orisa Popo religious group. Orisa Popo religious group does not form smaller groups across the community, but a single distinct group with a central leader, the King, other leaders are Araba, Oluwo/Iyalorisa, Awise, Aare Awo Akoda and Aseda among others

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– No

Notes: The religious group hierarchy does not follow this pattern. There is a clear hierarchical structure as listed from the king to Araba, then Oluwo and so on

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The hierarchy runs from the King to Araba, Oluwo/Iyalorisa then to Awise, Aare Awo then to Akoda/Aseda among others

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The leaders operate in form of a council, usually headed by Aare Awo. Aare Awo is to ensure that the spiritual ceremonies are executed in alignment with existing prescribed traditions.

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 5

Notes: There are five levels of hierarchy of leadership. However, each of these levels possesses a number of offices: Spiritual Leaders and High priests, Specialized Roles and Administrative Chiefs, Sub-Priest and Liturgical Officers, Initiated Devotees, Uninitiated Devotees and the Community

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

Notes: Powers are not brought from previous lives but inherited or transferred from one generation of devotees to the other especially among the leadership structure.

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: Power acquired by individuals in this current life are preserved and transferred to the coming generation within the hierarchical structure. Such deed could involve and intentional search for such powers.

↳ Powers are inherited:

– Yes

Notes: Powers are not brought from previous lives but inherited or transferred from one generation of devotees to the other especially among the leadership structure.

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: Powers are transferred from ancestors and encounter with other spiritual beings. Some leaders have encounters with some divinities or spiritual beings from whom they acquire spiritual powers.

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– Yes

Notes: Powers are transferred from one generation of mentors or teachers to another

especially when the mentor or teacher occupied an office the younger generation has just been inducted into within the leadership structure.

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– No

Notes: Powers are not attached to the office assumed but could be transferred from previous occupant of such office to ensure continuity of the legacy of the office.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

Notes: Leaders do not choose their own replacement. The council decides who the next leader will be after due consultation

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

Notes: Leaders do not choose the new leader. The council decides who the next leader will be after due consultation

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

Notes: Other leaders choose a leader. Through the council, such decision can only be taken after due consultation

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

Notes: Political leaders do not choose the leader except for the King. The indigenous council decides who the next leader will be after due consultation

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– Yes

Notes: Other leaders choose a replacement. The leaders who are members of the council congregate to decide who the next leader will be after due consultation

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

Notes: Members do not participate in the process of choosing a leader. Rather, the leaders through the council decides who the next leader will be after due consultation

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: Leaders carry out a thorough process which involves different kind of consultation. Among such consultation is divination of Ifa oracle

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

Notes: A leader's follower may find their leader culpable of some undeserving act and report such to higher leader or to the council. Leaders are not considered to be infallible.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: A leader may also find another leader culpable of some undeserving act and report such to another leader or to the council. No leader is considered to be infallible.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

Notes: it is unlikely that a political leader finds a fault in a leader within the religious group except such a political leader is an indigenous administrative leader. However, if

such is found, such an individual has the right and platform to report such to the appropriate quarters.

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Notes: The leaders are not believed to be infallible neither are they totalitarian. Therefore, the followers can question a decision of a leader but it must be done with respect or reported within the acceptable channel created to address such concerns.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The religious group depends on the oral scripture of Odu Ifa. Such scriptures are carefully preserved in myths, proverbs, folklore, folktales among others. These are often recited and passed down across generations for preservations.

↳ Are they written:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: Many times, Orunmila is quoted as being inspired by events leading to the standardization of Odu Ifa verses.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: This depends on the lenses with which Orunmila is viewed, either as a human who lived on the earth at some point or as a deity/divinity

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Ifa priests are trained to interpret the oral scriptures.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– No

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: There is no presence of monumental religious architecture except for the shrines. They also gather within the courtyard of the palace for instructions after major spiritual performance.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: Aside a central shrine located within the palace and a location called Oja-Igbo, there is no presence of monumental religious architecture. They also gather within the courtyard of the palace for instructions after major spiritual performance.

Is iconography present:

– No

Notes: There is no distinct iconography associated Orisa Popo. However, the Orisa employs some features of Obatala such as white clothes, calabash etc.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Myth has it that at the time it was institutionalized, the Orisa was originally sited along the major road that connects northern Nigeria to the southern part of the country, hence its name Orisa popo. Popo in Yoruba language means road/highway. (Although the geographical location we now call Nigeria had not become a country when the worship of Orisa Popo began). At that time, everyone headed to the

roadside to worship and make request from the Orisa.

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Notes: The sacred site is not motivated by environmental features but by location.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: There are no pilgrimages. Since Orisa Popo is essentially indigenous to Ogbomoso people, there are no people coming from outside the community for pilgrimage.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The spirit is considered to be eternal while the body dies. Orisa Popo group believes that when an individual dies a good death, the spirit of such an individual joins the ancestors of the lineage.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: The spirit is believed to be an ontological entity that leaves the body when someone dies.

The spirit can go somewhere to live again or be absorbed into the ancestral court.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: The spirit is most important component of a person, more of the essence of a person.

Notes: The spirit of an individual can be called out through esoteric power and deployed for other purposes that suit the possessor of the power.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: Afterlife is considered to be beyond this world. It is often conceived to be above the physical realm.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

Notes: The afterlife is considered to be beyond this world. It is often conceived to be above the sky and believed to be the habitat of Olodumare and the divinities

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

Notes: The concept of the afterlife is not described in terms of being below the earth. It is believed to be above and mostly for those who have a good moral living.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

Notes: The concept of the afterlife is not described in terms of a horizontal space. It is

believed to be above and mostly for those who have a good moral living.

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Notes: The concept of the afterlife is not described in terms of being other direction other than above the earth. It is believed to be above and mostly for those who have a good moral living and died a peaceful death.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: It is believed that dead person, especially those who were kind and of good moral can reincarnate and come back to life as new born babies to continue living with their loved ones

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: Group believes a person can reincarnate in human form in two dimensions: one is to come as a descendant within the family, often identified as a reincarnation of a certain ancestor. The second is if the individual is yet to complete his assignment but died as a result of an unfortunate incident, such an individual might surface in another location where no one from his previous life is present. Group believes that the moment someone from a previous life identifies him/her, the person will disappear from that environment.

↳ In animal/plant form:

– No

Notes: The group does not believe a human reincarnates in the form of an animal. The group believes that humans will always remain human even if they have to reincarnate multiple times.

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

Notes: The group does not believe a human reincarnates in the form of an inanimate object. The group believes that humans will always remain human even if they have to reincarnate multiple times.

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

Notes: The group does not believe a human reincarnate in non-human form. The group believes that individual humans will always remain human even if they have to reincarnate multiple times.

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: Group believes that an individual who lives a good moral life might be allowed by the gatekeeper of the afterlife to reincarnate to live with their beloved ones from a previous life. Whereas those who fall short of good moral living will not be permitted to reincarnate.

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No other form of reincarnation known to the field.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: Most adherents are affiliated with other religions, such as Christianity and Islam. They are usually buried in accordance with the other religious traditions. The Initiated Devotees are, however, buried according to indigenous customs, which include elaborate rituals

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: Burial in a tomb is always accompanied by various chants and incantations that repeatedly mention the name of the dead and his ancestral lineage.. Special sacrifice involving the killing of adire-irana, (literally means, clearing fowl or journey chicken)

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: The dead are buried with nothing except the white cloth or mat with which it is wrapped. The group believes humans brought nothing with them at birth and will therefore return taking nothing along

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Formal burial is present. It involves the initiates keeping vigil and a long burial procession to the tomb the second day.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: The group has no conception of a cenotaph. An individual has their grave if they die a good death. If otherwise, such an individual does not deserve an identifiable grave

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: The group has a burial place for prominent members of the group. Especially those who are higher title holders.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Notes: The group does not have a tomb-crypt for families within the group. Even though some families have burial ground/cemetery, they are not usually in the form of a crypt.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: The group does not have a belief that reinforces where people should be buried. Some members of the group might make certain demands of their relative as to where he/she wanted his or her remains buried. Such a request might involve being buried in his/her personal room, provided they are the owners of the house they live in

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: In the bush or under a tree

Notes: Individuals who died of some turbulent death, such as being struck by lightning or falling off a tree, might be buried under such a tree or in the bush where such an occurrence takes place.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: There is a belief in supernatural beings held to be in control of the affairs of the world. Sacrifices are offered to worship and to appease them.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes in Olodumare, the supreme being. He is believed to be the creator of the universe, and other beings are His ministers with different portfolios

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme deity possesses anthropomorphic attributes. He is also considered the creator of the universe.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes the supreme deity lives somewhere above the sky. However, He is not limited to the sky but seen as omnipresent

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: The group believes that the supreme deity does not live beneath the earth, but rather above the sky. The group often makes prayers to the supreme deity, looking into the sky in demonstration, like looking into his eyes.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– Yes

Notes: The group considers the supreme deity as the king of the universe. In the sense that he presides over everything that exists and direct the affairs of orun (heaven) and aye (earth) as he pleases.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

Notes: The monarch of the kingdom is seen as a sub-level to the supreme deity. As a matter of fact, the monarch is often praised as second in command to the Orisa.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: The supreme deity is not a kin relative to elites, he stands alone as one from whom every other derives their source and sustenance.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Notes: The supreme deity does not have a type of loyalty-connection to any class of people, but to everyone who does his bidding by living a good and moral life. The supreme deity has no special regard for individuals based on social class

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme deity is absolutely good. The group believes that even if there is evil, the evil is a result of human wrongdoing.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Omniscient and Omnipotent

Notes: The supreme deity is believed to know all things and can do all things

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: The group believes that the supreme deity knows everything about every

aspect of the universe and human affairs. In fact, the group believes the supreme deity knows the individual from the past to the future.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: The group believes there are no limitations to the knowledge of the supreme deity. Neither is the supreme deity confined to any space.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme deity possesses knowledge of all beings across all regions of the universe. The group believes that no knowledge escapes the supreme deity whether esoteric or exoteric.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme deity possesses knowledge of all beings across all regions of the universe. The group believes that no knowledge escapes the supreme deity, whether within or outside the sample region.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that, as no knowledge escapes the supreme deity, so also his eyes are able to cover the entire universe. The group believes the supreme deity sees whatever is done both in public and in secret

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the supreme deity sees everything across the universe at the same time. The group also believes the supreme deity sees

whatever is done both in public and in secret, in the light or in the dark

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that, as no knowledge escapes the supreme deity, so also his eyes are able to see through the thought of a human. The group also believes the supreme deity sees beyond tendered reason to actual motive of any human

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: The supreme deity knows everyone more than they know themselves. The group believes that the supreme deity makes human essence before each chooses their destiny and therefore knows everything about an individual

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: The supreme deity has both foreknowledge of everything and hindsight of everything. The group believes that the supreme being has everything in plan knows who will succeed at what beforehand.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Beyond the known

Notes: The group believes that the supreme deity knows more than humans can ever conceive. As they would often say, no one knows tomorrow except the supreme deity.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme deity can reward humans for their deeds. The group believes that the supreme deity rewards every good and evil act of a person. This has a way of motivating good deeds among the group.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that as much as the supreme deity rewards good deeds, he also punishes for evil deeds of an individual, as well as non-compliance with the ethical rules of the group, as instructed by the divine being.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: The group believes that the supreme deity's effect on the world is always direct and intentional. So his intervention is not accidental

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the supreme deity mostly dissipates positive influence upon the world. In cases where there are negative ones, it is to correct an anomaly

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the supreme deity exhibits negative emotions towards the world when human ere. It is also believed that such an exhibition is to bring about the necessary correction

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Notes: The group believes that the supreme high god does not possess hunger. They hold that hunger does not apply to him.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: The worship of the supreme deity is not often conceivable, as group appeals to the supreme deity through other deities, of which Orisa Popo is the most prominent of such within the sample region.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: incomprehensible

Notes: The group believes that the supreme deity cannot be fully comprehended by anyone. He is believed to be too vast for the mind to conceive and beyond what the mouth can tell

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

Notes: The communication of the supreme being is not conceived to be so frequent. except an individual does so through divination of other dinities.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the supreme being can communicate through dreams. But cannot be in person.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Group believes the supreme being can communicate through possession of lesser divinities. As a result, important information can be passed across.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the supreme being communicates through divination. Even though the divination might be directly through a medium, it is still believed it is the supreme being since the medium is standing as the

representative of the supreme being

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: The group believes that the supreme being can communicate through different and various means, of which religious specialists are one. But he is never limited in this approach.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: The group believes that since the monarch is a representative of the supreme deity, he can also communicate through him. However, the monarch does not have a monopoly on the supreme deity.

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: animal and natural environment

Notes: The supreme deity could communicate through any means he deems fit. The group further holds that everything the supreme deity created can serve as a means of communication for him.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the human spirit can be seen physically, but not in public, but for serious and private conversations that require divine intervention

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that there are times the human spirit can be felt but not necessarily seen. The holds that often, it has to be the ancestors of the living person in question.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that human spiritual knowledge is often restricted to their domain when they were alive. Also that are not so vast, in fact, they might be unaware of some issues.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: It is believed that the human spirit, though, knows more than humans possess, limited knowledge often restricted to their own lineage.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

Notes: The human spirit is restricted to its territory or family lineage. or area of dominance when alive within the sample region.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

Notes: The group holds that human knowledge does not cover matters outside the sample region. Because matters of the outside region belong to some other spirit domain.

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: It is believed that the human spirit can see members of its lineage anywhere in public. Because the human spirit, which will mostly be an ancestor, protects and guides members of their lineage

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: The human spirit can also see members of its lineage even in the dark. This is the reason it can be effective in protecting the relative.

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

Notes: The group holds that the human spirit does not possess such power to read the mind or see hidden motives. Even though some motive might be open to it, not the very hidden ones.

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– No

Notes: The group holds that personal essence is not open to the human spirit. It can see event taking place and the ones about to take place or plotted.

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

Notes: The group holds that the human spirit does not possess the knowledge to know what will happen in the future. But that such knowledge belongs to the supreme deity and some other few divinities.

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The group holds that the human spirit has very limited knowledge of the world. Which showcases the human limitation.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The human spirit can reward, but not as an end in itself, but as a means. They can only serve as an intermediary.

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

Notes: The human spirit can punish, but not as an end in itself, but as a means. They can only serve as an intermediary.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: The human spirit does not have an indirect causal effect on the world. Whatever they do must have been assigned by the supreme deity

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: The human spirit does have some memory of life. The group holds that not all that transpires in life can be remembered unless the supreme deity really wanted them to know.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The human spirit can exhibit positive emotion, but only as a medium. The human spirit does not possess such power.

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The human spirit can also exhibit negative emotion just as the positive ones, but still as a medium, not as an end in itself.

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the human spirit could possess hunger. This explains why some relatives will tell their deceased relative not to eat a millipede or earthworm, but

that whatever is being consumed where they are going is what they should eat.

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While the human spirit may possess other features, the field could not precisely say.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

Notes: The human spirit does not communicate with humans in waking and everyday life. Its communication is dependent on circumstances. Most times in times of a very difficult situation, unless summoned.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: The human spirit do communicate with humans in dreams. Its communication is dependent on circumstances. Most times in times of a very difficult situation, that might be drowning, it living relative.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: The human spirit does communicate through trance and spirit possession to communicate important matters that might hurt the relative if not properly taken seriously. Its communication is dependent on circumstances, most of the time in times of impending danger.

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

Notes: The human spirit does communicate with humans through divination. This is a process of summoning ancestors on matters that needs its intervention.

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

Notes: The human spirit does not only communicate through specialists. While it also communicates through specialists, there are several other means of communicating with humans.

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Notes: The human spirit does not communicate with humans through a monarch. Unless the monarch is a descendant. Also, there are many other means of communication

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While there may be other means of communication, field could not precisely say.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Notes: Orisa Popo is another prominent supernatural being around whom the religious group revolves. Orisa Popo is not seen physically, but it manifests in diverse ways, one of which is the granting of the requests of its devotees and worshippers

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: Orisa Popo cannot be physically felt in terms of physical touch. The group, however believed it can be felt emotionally, spiritually, and psychologically.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: Orisa Popo, the non-human supernatural deity, has a comprehensive knowledge of human affairs within the selected region. This is the reason devotees and worshippers approach it for any need, and he has been positively responsive.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: A non-human deity has knowledge restricted to their area of dominance, which is the sample region. Deities are often focused on their area of assignment as assigned by Olodumare.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Orisa Popo, has a comprehensive knowledge of human affairs within the selected region. The knowledge of the deity is robust and unrestricted.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

Notes: The group believes that Orisa Popo, has a comprehensive knowledge of human affairs within the sample region. However, they cannot tell of his potency outside the sample region since they believe the Orisa is specifically meant for the people within the sample region.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that Orisa Popo is the orisa whom Olodumare, the supreme deity, commits the affairs of the sample region to and as a result, he was given the power to see everything happening within the region.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that Orisa Popo is the orisa whom Olodumare, the supreme deity, commits the affairs of the sample region to and as a result, he was given the power to see everything happening within the region including in the dark.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

Notes: The non-human spiritual deity has comprehensive knowledge of the area of operation. However, hidden motives in the mind are only open to the supreme deity, Olodumare, who may or may not reveal them to the non-human deity.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that Orisa Popo is the orisa whom Olodumare, the supreme deity, commits the affairs of the sample region to and as a result, he was given the power to see everything happening within the region. Because of this even the personal essence of a person is open to the orisa

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that Orisa Popo is aware of what will happen to every individual in the future and what the individual's destiny says

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: solutions to problem

Notes: The group believes that Orisa Popo has the knowledge of every solution to every problem facing or that might face the sample region. He also has the power to avert them if the people do the right thing.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural deity can give a reward to a faithful worshipper. Orisa Popo is believed by the group to have issued countless rewards to its worshippers. It has also granted countless petitions according to their needs.

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural deity can punish a worshipper who eres. Orisa Popo is believed by the group to have punished countless worshippers who eres. However, the group maintains that he also forgives when an amendment is made through sacrifice. I

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: Orisa Popo is believed to have a direct impact on the world. The group believes nothing happens to the sample region that falls short of his intentional act.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that Orisa Popo is first and foremost a benefactor to the sample region. Its presence in so many ways brings a positive impact on the sample region.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that Orisa Popo is first and foremost a benefactor to the sample region; however, it can also exhibit some negative impact. It is believed that any negative exhibition from Orisa Popo will make society know that something is wrong that must be addressed as soon as possible.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the supernatural deity eats sacrifices, which is an indication that it possesses hunger. Eating is not entirely dependent on humans, according to the group's belief.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: compassionate

Notes: The group believes that Orisa Popo is a very compassionate deity, who understands the weakness of its worshippers yet embraces them all. The group also holds that Orisa Popo is a very tolerant deity by not insisting his worshippers must adhere to it alone.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: There are several divine beings, but they are not mixed; there are human spirit who are ancestors, and also there are supernatural beings who are not of human origin

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: Orisa Popo is the primary deity within the group. Although members of the group might adhere to other deities, those deities do not count as part of the group's supernatural beings.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts

and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that Orisa Popo monitors compliance with social norms. This is not an avenue to punish, but to see that there is order and that the society is protected from the consequences of non-compliance.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– No

Notes: The group believes that Orisa Popo cares about food. Orisa Popo, just like Obatala, does not accept palm oil, nor does it allow blood on its object of worship.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that Orisa Popo cares about the treatment of its space. Orisa Popo sacred spaces have to be treated with caution and reverence.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that every object connected to Orisa Popo has to be treated with reverence. Orisa Popo, just like Obatala, does not forbid palm oil and blood on its object of worship.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While the Orisa might care about many other things, the field is not able to tell at the moment.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that Orisa Popo has disdain for murder generally. As a result, frowns at

the murder of its designate.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: Orisa Popo does not tolerate murder of any kind. The deity holds human life as sacred and seeks to protect it.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: Orisa Popo does not tolerate murder of any kind. The deity holds human life as sacred and seeks to protect it.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes the Orisa frowns on people cheating on their spouses. They believe fidelity to the conjugal oath is expected of any adult.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes the Orisa frowns on sexual relationships among relatives. In fact, it is a taboo that must not be heard among the group.

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: same sex and bestiality

Notes: The group states that the Orisa frowns on sexual relationships between people of the same sex. It also abhors sexual relationships between humans and animals.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: For the group, lying is a disreputable thing as someone found of lying cannot be trusted. The group believes the orisa have strong disdain for someone who is not reliable or honest, which is the core of the group's moral code

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural deity believes that the oath made with a fellow human or deity must be kept. However, they emphasize that no one is under compulsion to make an oath and as a result, one must be willing to fulfil it.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: Orisa Popo encourages hard work and discourages laziness. The group often emphasizes that no matter how much an individual worships Orisa without hard work, such a worshipper will remain poor.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the use of sorcery to the detriment of others and the benefit of oneself is highly forbidden. It is believed that the deity will ensure that such a sorcerer reaps the consequences of their action

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that Orisa Popo frowns at any form of violence or fighting among worshippers, whether lethal or non-lethal. However, the orisa protect and fortified members in terms of war with external forces.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

Notes: Orisa Popo encourages dutifulness, reliability and hard work. The group often emphasizes that an individual who indulges in shirking cannot become an important person in life.

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural deity frowns at disrespect to anyone, especially elders. Matter of disrespect is encoded as part of the ethos of the Yoruba concept of omoluabi, which is expected of every member of the group.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: Gossip is one of the ill-mannered traits of anyone, according to the concept of omoluabi. The group believes that this concept was divinely given and upheld by Orisa Popo.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural deity frowns at any form of crime and at intervals rewards such an attitude with severe punishment after the individual has neglected all past warnings. Property crime is also one of those crimes that the deity abhors.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Ritual observance has a laid-down process which must be strictly adhered to, without which the ritual will not be accepted. The Orisa also holds such a process with high regard.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: Ritual is understood by the group as a process by which order is maintained or reinvented. Orisa Popo, like any other orisa, holds the performance of ritual in high esteem and frowns at its non-observance. The orisa also enforces the observance of prescribed rituals.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

Notes: The supernatural deity does not care about conversion. It embraces all members of the indigenous communities of the sample region, irrespective of their religious affiliation. Provided an individual comes from that community. The supernatural deity considers such an individual as his worshipper and child.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: Orisa Popo cares about fairness in everything. Fairness is one of the cardinal ethos of the concept of omoluabi, it is not only upheld by the orisa, but it is also enforced.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: Orisa Popo, with his connection to Obatala, cares about cleanliness so much that it requires so much purity in its shrines. This explains the use of white in all its things, why it forbade touching its object with blood, and the avoidance of palm oil.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: charitable

Notes: Orisa Popo is charitable and considerate of others' affairs.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: It can be done by the supernatural being itself. It is often a consequence of a certain misdeed.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: It can only be done by the supernatural being itself. It is often a consequence of a certain misdeed.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: It can be done by the cause-and-effect principle. It is often a consequence of a certain misdeed either to humans or nature.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Field has no knowledge of other entities that might be responsible for such.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: It can be done by the supernatural deity itself to enforce compliance with certain rituals or religious prescription. It is often a consequence of a certain deed/misdeed.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: It can be done by the supernatural deity itself to enforce compliance with group social norms. It is often a consequence of a certain deed/misdeed.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

Notes: The supernatural deity does not inflict punishment to inhibit selfishness. Punishment meted out by the deity is often for the greater good of the society.

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: The supernatural deity does not inflict punishment at random. There is definitely a just cause for any punishment meted out by the deity.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: It is often necessary to correct an anomaly that might ultimately put society at serious risk

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that afterlife punishment or reward awaits everyone. Therefore, emphasis is placed on moral living here to ensure one gets reward rather than punishment in the afterlife

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Notes: Punishment in the afterlife could consist of serious displeasure, such that could be painful and overwhelming

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Punishment in the afterlife could consist of serious displeasure, such that it could be painful and overwhelming. Punishment could include homelessness among others

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Notes: Reincarnation is mostly meant for the reward of good people, not the ones who deserve punishment. People can be denied reincarnation as punishment.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Notes: Reincarnation is mostly meant for the reward of good people, not the ones who deserve punishment. People can be denied reincarnation as punishment.

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Field has no knowledge of other punishment at the moment.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Notes: Punishment in this life is mildly emphasized by the group. The group believes that some may receive some of their reward of their doings here, more punishment awaits them in the afterlife.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Notes: Group believes that bad luck might come to some because of their previous activities in this life. However, more punishment still awaits them in the afterlife

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– No

Notes: Group believes that political failure might be as a result of previous activities in this life. However, not more of a punishment as real and more punishment still awaits them in the afterlife

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Notes: Group believes that defeat in battle may be as a result of previous activities in this life. However, more punishment still awaits them in the afterlife

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: Group believes that crop failure and bad weather might be as a result of previous activities in this life. However, not more of a punishment as real and more punishment still awaits them in the afterlife

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

Notes: Group believes that a disaster on a journey might be as a result of previous activities in this life. However, not more of a punishment as real and more punishment still awaits them in the afterlife

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Group believes that mild sensory displeasure might be as a result of previous activities in this life. However, not more of a punishment as real and more punishment still awaits them in the afterlife

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Group believes that extreme sensory displeasure might be as a result of previous activities in this life. However, more punishment still awaits them in the afterlife.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: Group believes that sickness or bad health might be as a result of previous activities in this life. However, real and more punishment still awaits them in the afterlife

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

Notes: Group believes that impaired reproduction might be as a result of previous activities in this life. However, real and more punishment still awaits them in the afterlife

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: Group believes that bad luck on descendants might be a result of previous activities in this life. However, the individual will still receive real and more punishment still awaits them in the afterlife

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Group believes that irrespective of the punishment one might have received in this life, more await such an individual in the afterlife.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– No

Notes: In most of the cases, the cause or purpose of supernatural reward is not known other than that the person is known to be a good person or hard-working. However, when it's the other way round, people tend to want to know what is responsible for the unfortunate situation.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Group believes and lays emphasis on reward in the afterlife. This has become a motivating factor for living a good and moral life here in this life.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

Notes: Group believes that reward in the afterlife is predominantly of abundant pleasure. This has become a motivating factor for living a good and moral life here in this life.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: Group believes that reward in the afterlife is predominantly of abundant pleasure, although not conceived as extreme in anyway. This has become a motivating factor for living a good and moral life here in this life.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Notes: Group believes that reward in the afterlife is predominantly of abundant pleasure and therefore bring about eternal happiness. This has become a motivating factor for living a good and moral life here in this life.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– Yes

Notes: Group believes that reward in the afterlife could include reincarnation into a beloved. The individual is given the opportunity to reincarnate in the family he loved so he can be with them again. This and other rewards have become motivating factors for living a good and moral life here in this life.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

Notes: Group believes that one can only reincarnate into a beloved as a reward, but not a question of realm. The individual is given the opportunity to reincarnate in the family he loved so he can be with them again.

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Field does not know of any other specific rewards in the afterlife. Field holds that since no one has been to the afterlife and returned, there are many things not open to human understanding.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that supernatural reward could be given in this present world, and the group usually lays emphasis on this as well to encourage moral living.

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that supernatural reward could be given in this present world, and the group usually lays emphasis on this as well to encourage moral living. Good luck is one of such rewards that can be given to deserving individuals.

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that supernatural reward could be given in this present world, and the group usually lays emphasis on this as well to encourage moral living. Political success or power could be one of such rewards that can be given to deserving individuals.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that supernatural reward could be given in this present world, and the group usually lays emphasis on this as well to encourage moral living. Success in battle could be one of such rewards that can be given to deserving individuals.

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that supernatural reward could be given in this present world, and the group usually lays emphasis on this as well to encourage moral living. Peace and social stability could be one of such rewards that can be given to deserving individuals.

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that supernatural reward could be given in this present world, and the group usually lays emphasis on this as well to encourage moral living. Health

crops and favourable weather could be one of such rewards that can be given to deserving individuals.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that supernatural reward could be given in this present world, and the group usually lays emphasis on this as well to encourage moral living. Success on journeys could be one of such rewards that can be given to deserving individuals.

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

Notes: The group believes that supernatural reward could be given in this present world, and the group usually lays emphasis on this as well to encourage moral living. Sensory pleasure could be one of such rewards that can be given to deserving individuals.

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that supernatural reward could be given in this present world, and the group usually lays emphasis on this as well to encourage moral living. Sensory pleasure could be one of such rewards that can be given to deserving individuals. but not quantified as extreme

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that supernatural reward could be given in this present world, and the group usually lays emphasis on this as well to encourage moral living. Good health could be one of such rewards that can be given to deserving individuals.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that supernatural reward could be given in this present world, and the group usually lays emphasis on this as well to encourage moral living. Reproductive success could be one of such rewards that can be given to deserving individuals.

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that supernatural reward could be given in this present world, and the group usually lays emphasis on this as well to encourage moral living. Fortune for the descendant could be one of such rewards that can be given to deserving individuals.

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While there are numerous other blessings or rewards, the field is not able to apprehend any other specific one.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: There is no messianic belief among the religious group. Group is not in expectation of any messiah.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: There are no eschatological beliefs other than individual dying and reincarnating. However, reincarnation depends on the kind of life lived and the desire of the supreme divinity

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There are general rules prescribed by the religious group. The social norms are most to uphold the society and individual moral standards.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: There is no distinction between conventional and moral rules within the group. All rules are simply viewed as general.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Notes: There are virtues, but these virtues are not more central than other norms. The group encourages virtues such as cleanliness, sexual purity, hard work, integrity, truthfulness, honesty, and courage among others.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Membership in the religious group does not require sexual abstinence or celibacy. Membership is defined by indigeneity. Every indigene of the sample region is considered to be a member.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Membership in the religious group does not require constraint of sexual activity. Membership is defined by indigeneity. Every indigene of the sample region is considered to be a member.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: Membership in the religious group does not require castration. Membership is defined by indigeneity. Every indigene of the sample region is considered to be a member.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Membership in the religious group does not require fasting. Membership is defined by indigeneity. Every indigene of the sample region is considered to be a member.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on

desired foods):

– No

Notes: Membership in the religious group does not require a forgone opportunity for food, nor does it require abstinence from certain kind of food. Membership is defined by indigeneity. Every indigene of the sample region is considered to be a member.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: Membership in the religious group does not require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations. Membership is defined by indigeneity. Every indigene of the sample region is considered to be a member.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: Membership in the religious group does not require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds. Membership is defined by indigeneity. Every indigene of the sample region is considered to be a member.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: Membership in the religious group does not require human sacrifice of any kind. Membership is defined by indigeneity. Every indigene of the sample region is considered to be a member.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: Membership in the religious group does not require human sacrifice of any kind. Membership is defined by indigeneity. Every indigene of the sample region is considered to be a member.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: Membership in the religious group does not require suicide or the death of anyone. Membership is defined by indigeneity. Every indigene of the sample region is considered to be a member.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Membership in the religious group does not require sacrifice of property of any kind. Membership is defined by indigeneity. Every indigene of the sample region is considered to be a member.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: Membership in the religious group does not require a sacrifice of time. The religious group does not meet regularly, just occasional festivity and a ritual ceremony.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: Membership in the religious group does not require risk taking. Membership is defined by indigeneity. Every indigene of the sample region is considered to be a member.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Notes: Membership in the religious group does not require accepting ethical precepts as a condition of membership. Membership is defined by indigeneity. Every indigene of the sample region is considered to be a member.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: Membership in the religious group does not require marginalization by out-group members. The religious group and the deity embrace everyone without marginalizing anyone

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private,

household):

– No

Notes: Membership in the religious group does not require participation in any scale of rituals. Membership is defined by indigeneity. Every indigene of the sample region is considered to be a member.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Notes: Membership in the religious group does not require participation in any large-scale rituals. Membership is defined by indigeneity. Every indigene of the sample region is considered to be a member. The religious group considers indigene of the sample religion who practiced other faith in diaspora and who by no means participate in any ritual as a bona fide member of the group, so far they are indigenes of the community.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Notes: There are no extra-ritual in-group markers present within the religious group. Every indigene of the sample region is considered to be an in-group member, without any extra ritual.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group employs the term "Ogbomoso Ajilete" that is One who wakes up and is lifted up above every other community or people who fold arms in the presence of war and still won the battle" as fictive kinship terminology.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: The kinship terminology is universal for any indigene of the sample region. It is used by all as a means of identification, even in diaspora.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Notes: The kinship terminology is widespread even beyond the shores of Ogbomoso. It is used by all as a means of identification, even in the diaspora.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Notes: The kinship terminology is common among the indigenes of the sample region. In fact, several businesses within the sample region use the terminology for their business name.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Notes: Ogbomoso is a kingdom that has several other communities headed by chiefs who report to the Soun, the king of Ogbomoso.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not have an industrialized famine relief. However, the religious group has its own unique way of providing relief during famine. The religious specialist consults the oracle to ascertain the reason for the draught and appease the gods through sacrifice to avert it.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There is relief when needed from the King's palace. There could also be relief from NGOs and the government either at the local, the state, or federal level.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not provide institutionalized poverty relief. The group believes the institution does not have such financial resources to provide such relief.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: There is no poverty relief available for the adherent through other institutions. Generally, poverty relief packages are scarcely available within and outside the sample region.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not provide an institutionalized care system for the elderly and infirm. The group does not have the resources to provide such care due to economic hardship and instability. Each family in the sample region provide care for their childre, elderly and other vulnerable folks within the family circle.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: There is no institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to adherents through other institutions(s) other than the religious institutions in question. There are generally no such interventions for members of indigenous communities within or around the sample region.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: The religious institution does not provide education to its adherents. This is so because provision of educational facilities is capital intensive and the religious group does not have such financial capability.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: The government, private, and business individuals provide education for members of the group. The opportunity is open to both male and female.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group has a formal bureaucracy that runs within its administrative structure. The bureaucracy runs through the different levels to the king as the head. It is built within the indigenous administrative system.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The adherent interacts with other institutional bureaucracies like the government at the local, state, and federal levels.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not provide public food storage for the members of the group or the community. The religious group is of the view that its financial resources are not adequate for such provision.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Public food storage is not provided for the members of the group or the community by other institution(s) other than the religious group. There are generally no such interventions for members of

indigenous communities within or around the sample region.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: The religious group does not provide water management system for the members of the group or the community. The religious group believes its financial resources are not adequate for such provision.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Water management system is not provided for the members of the group or the community by other institutions (s) other than the religious group. There are generally no such interventions for members of indigenous communities within or around the sample region.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not provide transportation infrastructure for the members of the group or the community. The religious group believes its financial resources are not adequate for such venture.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The state government and private individuals cater for the transportation needs of the region at a cost. The system functions with private individuals owning most of the vehicles, while the union of drivers also owns some. It is regulated by the union of drivers and the state government.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not levy taxes or tithes on its members. The tax levy system is entirely under the purview of the government. However, the group might receive donations from individuals and subventions from the palace.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The government at different levels levied taxes on members of the group. The adherents are mandated to pay taxes as their constitutional duty.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not provide an institutionalized police force. Only the government at the federal level has the exclusive right to operate an institutionalized police force.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group interacts with the national police force. It is the exclusive duty of the police to protect the life and property of everyone. It is on this basis that there are police force stations in the sample region.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not provide institutionalized judges, even though an adherent might be a judge. The nation and state run the judicial system. However, the group has its own indigenous system that hears adherents' cases as long as they are minor non-criminal matters.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group interacts with the judicial system provided by the government at the federal and state levels. The group's system of dealing with tribute might also refer criminal or serious disputes to the judicial system.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not have the power to execute any individual. Matters of serious concern will be addressed through the established judicial system of the state.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: In the past matters of serious concern might warrant sending offenders into exile. This has changed in modern times, since an individual can decide to seek redress in the state's court of law.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: In ancient times, the group might carry out corporal punishments. However, such rarely happens in modern times.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Notes: The group does not ostracize its members, since membership is based on indigenization. Ostracism can't be effective since the individual cannot be excluded from participating in rituals.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: Property can be seized if acquired wrongfully. An individual can also be asked to pay a certain amount or bring a certain element as a fine for their offence.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: The government, through its judicial arm, can sentence an adherent to execution. This can only be done by the pronouncement of a judge who hears the case. Such execution must also be approved by the state governor before it can be carried out.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Notes: No institution can send an adherent on exile. It is currently against the constitutional rights of any citizen of the sample region.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: The government does not carry out corporal punishment, but might sentence the individual to prison for their unlawful actions.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: The government, through its judicial arm, can ostracize by putting the offender in prison. This can only be done by the pronouncement of a judge who hears the case.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: The government, through its judicial arm, can seize the property of the offender. This can only be done by the pronouncement of a judge who hears the case.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not have a formal legal code. The norms and rules of the group are, at best, oral and passed down to generations orally.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The members of the religious group are subject to the constitution of the country and laws made by the state government. The adherents can be punished under the provision of the law.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not possess an institutionalized military. The military is under the purview of the government. However, it has its own warriors who might defend it from indigenous external aggression.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Adherents might participate in the nation's military, but as individual citizens, not as representatives of the religious group. The nation's military is independent of the religious group.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The adherents are protected by the military of the state and are also subject to it. As a citizen of Nigeria, it is the duty of the military to protect the nation from external aggression.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not possess its own distinct written language other than the Yoruba language. Although there might be a form of variation with other Yoruba-speaking people, it does not constitute a different language.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Yoruba language is not an exclusive religious language. It is the language in which the religious group expresses itself and carry out its worship and performances.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group uses the Yoruba language, which is an element of Yoruba culture. Yoruba language is the language of all Yoruba groups with little variations

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not possess a separate formal calendar. The group uses the agrarian calendar.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The agrarian calendar is the calendar used by the religious group. All its activities and ceremonies are carried out using the agrarian calendar. Although there are traditional means of counting days and months among the indigenous group. This only survives in this age as relics of the Yoruba indigenous/traditional system.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not provide food for itself. However, a reasonable population of the sample region are farmers who cultivate their own plantation. However, the plantations are not exclusively produced by them. The most prominent farm produce are cashew (Cashew nut), mangoes, yam and corn/maize.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: There are no specific institutions providing food for the adherents of the religious group. Members of the religious group survive on food produced by non-institutional actors like themselves and other farmers.

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